

SURXANDARYO VILOYATI SHAROITDA KUZGI BUG‘DOY EKINLARIDA *EURYGASTER INTEGRICEPS* PUT VA *OULEMA MELANOPUS* L TARQALISHI HAMDA ZARARLANISH DARAJASI

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Abstract. In April 2025, the population density and damage levels caused by *Eurygaster integriceps* and *Oulema melanopus* were assessed in wheat fields of the Surxondaryo region. The average density of *Eurygaster integriceps* was recorded at 1.91 individuals per square meter, with an average spike damage rate of 4.96%. In the case of *Oulema melanopus*, an average of 16.8 individuals were observed per 100 wheat stems, with flag leaf damage reaching 24.8%.

Keywords: Wheat, pest, chewing insect, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Oulema melanopus*, larval stage, adult stage.

Аннотация. В апреле 2025 года на пшеничных полях Сурхандарьинской области были выявлены численность вредителей *Eurygaster integriceps* и *Olema melanopus*, а также степень повреждения колосьев и флаговых листьев. Средняя численность *Eurygaster integriceps* составила 1,91 особи на 1 м², при этом средний уровень повреждения колосьев достиг 4,96%. В отношении вредителя *Olema melanopus* установлено, что на 100 стеблей пшеницы в среднем отмечено 16,8 личинок, а степень повреждения флаговых листьев составила 24,8%.

Ключевые слова: пшеница, вредитель, листогрызущий, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Olema melanopus*, личинка, имаго.

Anatasiya. 2025-yil aprel oyida Surxandaryo viloyatidagi bug‘doy dalalarida *Eurygaster integriceps* va *Olema melanopus*ning soni, boshqoq va bargda zararlanish darajasi aniqlandi. Bunda *Eurygaster integriceps* 1m² o‘rtacha 1,91 dona bo‘lib boshqoqlarning zararlanishi o‘rtacha 4,96%, *Olema melanopus* zararkunandasida esa 100 ta bug‘doy poyadagi bayroq barglarda o‘rtacha 16,8 dinani, barglarning zararlanishi 24,8% ko‘rsatdi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Bug‘doy, zararkunanda, kemiruvchi, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Olema melanopus*, lichinka, imago bosqichi.

Kirish. Turli iqlim sharoitlariga moslashuvchanligi tufayli, *Triticum* spp. dunyoning ko‘plab hududlarida keng miqyosda yetishtiriladi va dunyo aholisining yarmidan ortig‘i uchun asosiy oziq-ovqat manbai hisoblanadi. Global miqyosda bug‘doy ishlab chiqarish hajmi taxminan 770 million tonnani tashkil etadi va Turkiya 17,5 million tonna bilan o‘ninchi o‘rinda turadi [5;10].

Global isish va iqlim o‘zgarishi ta’sirida yuzaga kelayotgan abiotik stress omillari bug‘doy uchun jiddiy tahdid tug‘dirmoqda. Shuningdek, ayrim davrlarda zararkunandalardan va kasalliklardan populyatsiyasining iqtisodiy zarar me’yoridan oshib ketishi ham kuzatilmoqda [7;20]. So‘nggi yillarda bug‘doyga jiddiy zarar yetkazayotgan zararkunandalardan biri bu don barg qo‘ng‘izi (*Oulema melanopus*) va zararli xasva (*Eurygaster integriceps*) hisoblanadi [3;29]. Don barg

qo‘ng‘izi ixtisoslashgan fitofag bulib, ko‘plab don yetishtiruvchi mamlakatlarda bug‘doyning eng muhim zararkunandasi hisoblanadi [9;24].

Ko‘plab tadqiqotchilarning takidlashicha dunyo buyicha 100 ga yaqin Shilimshiq qurt *Olema spp*, mavjud bo‘lib, ular asosan mo‘tadil va tropik o‘lkalarda yashab, *Amaranthaceae*, *Commelinaceae*, *Compositae*, *Cyperaceae*, *Gramineae*, *Leguminosae* oilalariga mansub o‘simliklarda uchrashi takidlangan [28]. Bu oilalar echida ayniqsa Gramineae oilasining ko‘plab yovvoyi va xonakilashtirilgan o‘simliklarni uchrab zarari yuqori ekanligi aniqlangan [4;13].

Bahorda ob-havo sharoiti 10-12 °C dan oshganda shilimshiq qo‘rt qo‘ng‘izi (imago) qishlovdan chiqib, boshqoli barglarini tomirlari bo‘ylab kemirib, tor va cho‘zilgan teshiklarni hosil qilib zarar etkazadi [28].

Kimyoviy himoya choralari va boshqa profilaktik tadbirlar ko‘rilmagan taqdirda, *Eurygaster integriceps* arpa hosilining 30 foizigacha va bug‘doy hosilining 50–100 foizigacha yo‘qotilishiga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin [2;17]. *O. melanopus* zarari bahorgi bug‘doyda 55%, kuzgi bug‘doyda esa 23% gacha hosil yo‘qotilishiga olib kelgan [9;23]. Voyaga yetmagan lichinkalar kattalarga nisbatan ancha jiddiy zarar keltiradi, chunki ular tana og‘irligiga nisbatan o‘simlik biomassasini 1 dan 10 baravargacha ko‘proq iste‘mol qilishi aniqlangan [6;22].

Tadqiqot materiallari va uslublari.

Mamlakatimizda bug‘doy hosildorligiga ziddiy xavf solayotgan zararkunandalarni aniqlash va monitoring qilish maqsadida 2025-yilda Surxandaryo viloyatida joylashgan kuzgi bug‘doy dalalarida tajribalar o‘tkazildi. Zararli xavsa zararkunandasi bug‘doy dalalarida mavjudligini aniqlash uchun xo‘jaliklarda har biri 0,25 m² (50x50 sm) bo‘lgan 20 ta namunalar tanlab olinib, zararkunandalar soni hisoblablandi. Shilimshiq qo‘rt qo‘ng‘izi va lichinkalari 1m² maydonda zichligiga qarab diagonali bo‘ylab bir-biridan teng masofada 10 ta joyidan o‘rtasida o‘sadigan 25 ta o‘simlikdan tasodifiy yig‘ilgan 50 bargda (bayroq bargi va yuqoridan ikkinchi va uchinchi barglar) namuna olinib hisoblandi.

Zararkunandalarning paydo bo‘lish vaqti, populyatsiyasini hisoblash umumiy qabul qilingan Polyakov I va b., (1984); Osmolovsky G.E., Bondarenko N.V., (1980), Golub V.B. va boshqalar (1980), Doroxova G.I. (1995), usullarga muvofiq amalga oshirildi [16;19;26;27]. Zararkunandaning soni va bug‘doyzordagi populyatsiyasi zichligini aniqlashda logarifmlar shkalasidan [11], hamda shikastlanish darajasini aniqlashda Stamenkov, S va Pankov, L. (1991) 0-5 shkalasidan hamda Rouag N va b., (2012) uslublarida amalga oshirildi [20;21].

Tadqiqot natijalari

Surxandaryo viloyatida kuzgi bug‘doy ekilgam dalalarda *Eurygaster integriceps* va *Olema melanopus* zararkunandalarning uchrash darajasi va zarari monitoring qilindi (1-jadval). Surxandaryo viloyatda jami 89 325 ming gektar maydonga kuzgi g‘alla ekilib parvarishlanmoqda.

Termiz tumanidagi Ingichka Tolali Paxtachilik ITI 12,3 gektarli grom navli bug‘doy dalasida *E. integriceps* 1 m² da 1,6 dona borligi, boshqolarining zararlanishi 4,3%, 100 ta bug‘doy poyadagi 14,3 dona *O. melanopus* lichinkalari uchrashi, bayroq barglarining zararlanishi 26,3% ekanligi aniqlangan. Xuddi shu tumandagi “Elyor o‘g‘li Asilbek” fermer xo‘jaligining 13,4 gektar maydonida *E. integriceps* 1 m² da 1,8 dona, boshqolarining zararlanishi 4,6%, *O. melanopus* 17,8 dona lichinkalari uchrashi, bayroq barglarning zararlanishi darajasi esa 23,1% ni ko‘rsatdi.

Muzrabot tumani “Mamanazarov Xo‘janazar Bobo” fermer xo‘jaligining 6,3 gektarli bug‘doy dalasida monitoring olib borilganda, *E. integriceps* 1 m² da 2,1 dona borligi, boshqolarining zararlanishi 5,6%, 100 ta bug‘doy poyadagi 18,0 dona *O. melanopus* lichinkalari

uchrashi, bayroq barglarining zararlanishi 26,6% ekanligi, hamda shu tumandagi “Odil Fayz” fermer xo‘jaligining 7,3 gektarli maydonida

E. integriceps 2,0 dona, boshloqlarining zararlanishi 5,0%, *O. melanopus* 16,4 dona lichinkalari uchrashi, bayroq barglarning zararlanishi darajasi esa 24,3% bo‘ldi.

Angor tumani “Bashir Bobo” fermer xo‘jaligining 11,5 gektarli bug‘doy dalasi monitoring qilinganda 1 m² da *E. integriceps* 2,3 dona ekanligi, boshloqlarining zararlanishi 5,8%, 100 ta bug‘doy poyadagi 16,0 dona *O. melanopus* borligi, bayroq barglarining zararlanishi esa 23,6% ekanligi aniqlangan. Shu tumanning “Angor Fayzi” fermer xo‘jaligining 20,4 gektarli dalasining 3,3 gektarli qismida esa

E. integriceps 1,7 dona, boshloqlarining zararlanishi 4,5%, 17,2 dona *O. Melanopus* borligi, bayroq barglarining zararlanishi 25,4% ekanligi hisob ketob ishlarida aniqlandi.

Xulosa. Surxandaryo viloyati sharoitda kuzgi bug‘doy dalalarida *Eurygaster integriceps* va *Olema melanopus*ning paydo bo‘lish va zararlanish darajasi 3 ta tuman, 6 ta fermer xo‘jaligida olib brogan tajrinalarimizda shu narsa ma‘lum bo‘ldiki *Eurygaster integriceps* 1m² o‘rtacha 1,91 dona bo‘lib boshloqlarning zararlanishi o‘rtacha 4,96%, *Olema melanopus* zararkunandasida esa 100 ta bug‘doy poyadagi bayroq barglarda o‘rtacha 16,8 dinani, barglarning zararlanishi 24,8% ekanligi aniqlandi.

jadval-1

Surxandaryo viloyati tumanlari bo'yicha fermer xo'jaliklarining kuzgi bug'doy dalalarida Eurygaster integriceps va Olema melanopus
0,25 m² soni va zararlantirish darajasi, 2025 yil.

T/r	Viloyat	Tuman	Fermer xo'jaligi	Gektari	1 m ² da <i>E. integriceps</i> soni (dona)	100 ta bug'doy poyadagi <i>O.</i> <i>melanopus</i> soni (dona)	1 m ² da <i>E. integriceps</i> zararlantirish darajasi (%)	100 ta bug'doy poyadagi barglarning <i>O. melanopus</i> zararlantirish darajasi (%)
1.	Surxandaryo	Termiz	Ingichka tolali paxtachilik ITI	12,3	1,6	17,8	4,3	26,3
			Elyor o'li Asilbek	13,4	1,8	15,6	4,6	23,1
			Mamanazarov Xo'janazar Bobo	6,3	2,1	18,0	5,6	26,6
		Muzrabot	Odil Fayz	7,3	2,0	16,4	5,0	24,3
			Bashir Bobo	11,5	2,3	16,0	5,8	23,6
			Angor Fayzi	3,3	1,7	17,2	4,5	25,4
	Angor							

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